

CHARACTERISTICS OF EMOTION APPEARANCE IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

¹Ibraimov Xolboy Ibragimovich, ²Khurbaliev Tarmiza Latipovna

¹Director of the Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after T.N.Kori Niyoz. Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

²Chirchik State Pedagogical University, doctor of pedagogical sciences (DSc), Professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10288250>

Abstract. *The article provides information about the psychological and physiological characteristics of emotions and feelings. The theories of psychological scientists regarding the manifestation of emotional states in the period of human and preschool age are given.*

Keywords: *emotion, feeling, sensitive, social intelligence, affect, mood, stress, extros, sthenic, asthenic.*

Emotion means mental excitement, mental movement. Feeling is the state of pleasure and enjoyment while listening to a good piece of music. The same emotion that comes from hearing a piece of music played poorly is experienced as a negative emotion, such as disgust. Fear or panic as an emotion, that is, a specific attitude towards certain objects, their combinations or their position in life, can be forgiven in different emotional processes. Sometimes a person runs away from something scary, and sometimes he freezes and trembles because of fear, he can panic and act against danger out of desperation.

Emotions are divided into **sthenic** and **asthenic** types according to their affectivity. It is a state that encourages sthenic actions, thoughts, and overexerts. Being happy in this, a person is ready to "crush the mountain". Feeling sympathy for his friend, he looks for a way to help him. In other cases, asthenic emotions are characterized by slowness or indifference, the experience of emotions makes a person feel relaxed. His "legs tremble" because of fear. In some cases, a person gets carried away by a strong feeling, immerses himself in imagination and becomes obsessed with himself.

As a result of scientific research, scientists have come to the conclusion that emotional states and their development are formed in childhood. Nowadays, adults are busy with the physical and mental development of children. The sensitive period of emotional development of children in preschool age is missed, although it is closely related to the development of the child's personality and is expressed by their psychological development and success in the social environment. This problem is relevant in connection with children's social and emotional intelligence. Scientists have come to the conclusion that if a person has developed emotional and social intelligence, he will be successful in communication, it will have a positive effect on learning and playing.

Deficiencies in the development of emotional state and emotional intelligence in preschool children make it difficult for them to express their personal feelings. All factors cause mutual conflicts between children, disagreements in interpersonal relationships, create negative situations such as nervousness, hyperactivity, anger, shyness, lack of attention. As a result, children's socialization is difficult, and it even affects later stages of development. Different forms of experiencing feelings - emotion, affect, mood, stress, love, affection, and finally, in a narrow sense, feelings make up the emotional sphere of a person. They regulate human behavior, are considered

a living source of knowledge, an expression of complex and multifaceted relationships between people.

Emotions help to identify things that meet a person's needs. Interest, as a separate form of need manifestation, always has an emotional tone. Feelings subjectively calculated for a person appear as a sign of how the process of satisfying his needs is going [1; 292-b].

Psychologists believe that emotion is manifested in situations such as personal feelings, affect, mood, and stress. Emotion is a psychological process, related to instinct, need, motive, and the occurrence of situations and events in a person's life. Emotional stress in children is physiologically caused by the stress of adaptation of the body to the negative effects of the environment, as a result of long-term storage of negative emotions. Strong excitement (stress) is a special form of experiencing emotions that are close to an affective state, but are close to moods according to the duration of their experience - a state of strong excitement (stress (derived from the English word - pressure, tension), or emotional tension. Emotional tension It occurs in situations where there is danger, when a person is upset, ashamed, in danger, etc. Danger makes a person more alert, forces him to act boldly and courageously. In a state of emotional stress, the behavior of an individual depends on the type of the nervous system of a person. Strongly depends on the strength or weakness of mental processes.

According to K.E.Izard, S.Tomkins, emotions constitute a motivational system. If people are always under the influence of emotions, it will have a negative effect on their morals, resulting in psychosomatic diseases [9]

Ch.Darwin bases the similarity of animal and human behavior on the evolutionary theory of emotions. Evolution is not only a biological and psychological factor, but also emerged as a coordinating mechanism for emotion. Physical changes affect the emotional state of a person. Expressions of emotions such as fear, anger, and frustration appear based on their lifestyle and its various factors.

According to James-Lange's theory of emotion, we can control our emotions through our actions in the fulfillment of our desired desires [9].

However, L.S.Vygotsky rejects this theory. And he puts forward the idea that emotion is the highest emotional value of a person, and it grows aesthetically, intellectually, and spiritually [4].

D.Watson also criticizes James-Lange's idea. It justifies the manifestation of emotion in three main forms:

1. Fear
2. Anger
3. Love

He distinguishes these forms according to the nature of human behavior and physiological condition. Forms of emotion are innate or occur under the influence of changes in a person's life. So, based on theories about emotions, it can be said that changes in human internal organs reflect his emotions.

Emotions are one of the more free manifestations of a person's personality, which is manifested together with cognitive processes and voluntary control of behavior and activity. The content of emotions is the stable attitude of the person to what he takes and does with him. Emotions in a narrow sense reflect the attitude of a person towards the object of his stable needs embodied in the orientation of his personality. Therefore, with its stability, the life of the subject is determined by its duration, which is measured not by hours, but by months and years. Feelings will

have a concrete character. They occur due to facts, events, people and situations that cause the subject to express a stable positive or negative reaction.

As S.L. Rubinstein noted, "emotions are embodied as the subjective existence of desires for a person" [11]. A mother who is angered by her daughter's behavior may feel angry. But after some time passes, his love for his daughter prevails, his mistake is forgotten and he can forgive his daughter.

Conclusion

In short, it is important for educators and parents to understand that the situations listed above depend on the social environment and adults around children. It is important for educators and parents to carefully observe the emotional state of each child, control their manners, behavior, and know the reasons for negative changes in the child's psyche. It is necessary to solve the problem situations in the child's life in the most effective ways in cooperation with the educator and the psychologist.

REFERENCES

1. Галустова О. В. Шпаргалка по истории психологии: учеб. пособие. -М.: ТК Велби, 2005.-48 с.
2. Вохидов М. Болалар психологияси. Т.-1982- 290 б.
3. Виготский Л.С. Возрастная и педагогическая психология: М.: Изд-во Моск. ун-та, 1992.- 272с.
4. Виготский Л.С. Вопросы детской психологии-СПб.: Союз, 1997.-224 с
5. Дарвиш О.В. Возрастная психология. Учеб.пособие для студ. высш. учеб. Заведений. М.: Владос-пресс, 2003.-341 с.
6. Давлетшин. М.Г., Ш.Дўстмухамедова ва бошқ. Ёш даврлари ва педагогик психология.Ўқув методик қўлланма.-Т.: 2004-129 б.
7. Крайг Г., Бокум Д. Психология развития. СПб.: Питер, 2005. 940 с
8. Леонтев А.Н. Лекции по общей психологии. М.-2000.508-б.
9. Марцинковская ТД. Детская практическая психология: Учебник/ М.: Гардарики, 2003.-255.
9. Петровский А. В. Умудий психология. Т.-1992- 313 б.
10. Психология развития. Под ред. А. К. Болотовой и О. Н. Молчановой. М.-2005, 524 с.
11. Хурвалиева Т.Л. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda emotsional zo'riqishni bartaraf etishning samarali yo'llari. Maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'limning dolzarb masalalari:muammo, yechimlar va rivojlanish istiqbollari. Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani materiallari. Farg'ona. 2023, 29-33 b.
12. Хурвалиева Т.Л, R.X.Nosirova N.X.Ma'rupova. Possibilities of Using Art Therapy in Preschool Education. International journal of online and biomedical engineering E-ISSN:2626-8493Journal URL: <http://ijobe.org>. Scopus URL: <https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/Scope: Engineering: General Engineering>. 5842-5848 p.
13. Ibragimovich Kh.I. Peculiarities of using credit-module technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal. - 2021. - P. 209-214.
14. Ibraimov Kh. "Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system." International journal of discourse on innovation,

- integration and education 1 (2020): 6-15.
15. Ibragimov, X., Abdullayeva Sh. "Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)." T.: Fan va texnologiya 288 (2008).
 16. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –T., “Shaffof”, 2023, 416-bet.
 17. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
 18. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
 19. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
 20. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
 21. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организatsiya samostoyatel'noy raboty studentov v usloviyakh tsifrovizatsii vuzovskogo obrazovaniya //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.